

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5542179>

The first find of the male *Chondrometopum arcuatum* (Diptera: Ulidiidae: Pterocallini)

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The first find of the male *Chondrometopum arcuatum* (Diptera: Ulidiidae: Pterocallini). Schulten, D. & Kameneva, E.P. — The first photograph of the picture-winged fly *Chondrometopum arcuatum* Hendel, 1909 taken in the nature shows that this species has the head shape and wing venation and pattern sexually dimorphic as in *C. bifenestratum* Kertész, 1913, including the presence of the horn-like genal projections. A modified and illustrated key to species is provided.

Key words: Diptera, picture-winged flies, Peru, sexual dimorphism, key.

Перша знахідка самця *Chondrometopum arcuatum* (Diptera: Ulidiidae: Pterocallini). Шульген, Д. і Каменєва, О.П. — Найперше фото мухи-стрічкокрилки *Chondrometopum arcuatum* Hendel, 1909 зроблене в природі, показує, що форма голови, а також жилкування і візерунок крила цього виду мають статевий диморфізм, як і в *C. bifenestratum* Kertész, 1913, включаючи наявність рогоподібних виростів на щоках. Наведено ілюстровану таблицю для визначення видів.

Ключові слова: двокрилі, мухи-стрічкокрилки, Перу, статевий диморфізм, ключ для визначення.

Introduction

The picture-winged flies of the genus *Chondrometopum* Hendel, 1909 occur in the Neotropical Region from Costa Rica to Panama (Hendel, 1909; Steyskal, 1968; Kameneva, 2004). The genus includes three species, *Chondrometopum arcuatum* Hendel, 1909, *C. bifenestratum* Kertész, 1913 and *C. leve* Hendel, 1914.

Kameneva (2004) has summarized all available, scarce collection data and provided a key and illustrations, including previously unknown males of *C. bifenestratum* and *C. leve*, whereas *C. arcuatum* remained known only from the original description based on the holotype female (Hendel, 1909 a, 1909 b).

Chondrometopum arcuatum Hendel, 1909 (Figs 4–6)

Material. Peru: ACP Panguana, 9.62°S, 74.93°W, 20.09.2019, 1 ♂ (Schulten) (photo in the nature).

Distribution. Guyana (Steyskal, 1968), Peru.

Remarks. All the species of *Chondrometopum* show strong sexual dimorphism in their wing venation and pattern (Figs 2–3, 5–6, 9–10), with pterostigma enlarged and deepening posteriorly in males and only slightly modified in females (Kameneva, 2004). In addition, females of *C. arcuatum* and *C. bifenestratum* were known to have widened head (Figs 4, 8), and male of *C. bifenestratum* having it even more wide with horn-like genal processes (Fig. 7), and

C. leve was found to have heads of both male and female unmodified, as in many other Pterocallini (Fig. 1).

The photograph of a picture-winged fly taken by DS in Peruvian Amazonia (Fig. 5) was identified by EPK as *C. arcuatum*. This is a male, which possesses genal “horns”

similar to those in male *C. bifenestratum*, but clearly differing by the other characters given in the key below, including the abdominal tergites surface and vestiture.

The only key to species provided by Kameneva (2004) can be modified as follows:

A Key to Species of *Chondrometopum*

(modified from Kameneva, 2004)

- 1 Head as wide as thorax or narrower, neither transverse, nor with genal processes. Thorax subshining brown. Acrostichal setae absent in both sexes. Wing venation and pattern as on Figs 2–3; its length < 3.5 mm (2.0–3.0). *C. leve*
 — Head wider than thorax, in males with horn-like processes on genae (Figs 4–5, 7–8). Thorax gray microtrichose. Acrostichal setae often present in females, absent in males. Wing length more than 3.5 mm (4.0–5.0). 2

Figs 1–3. *Chondrometopum leve*: 1 — head laterally 2–3 — wing (2 — male, 3 — female).
(redrawn from Kameneva, 2004)

2. Abdominal tergites shining black, rough, with smoothed papillae at bases of setulae. Wing: preapical crossband separated from basal dark pattern by complete hyaline area. Male wing pattern as on Fig. 5; female as on Fig. 6. *C. arcuatum*
 — Abdominal tergites gray microtrichose, smooth, with shining black or brown spots at bases of setulae. Female: preapical crossband joined with basal dark pattern along vein R_{2+3} . Male wing pattern as on Fig. 9; female as on Fig. 10. *C. bifenestratum*

Figs 4–6. *Chondrometopum arcuatum*: 4 — head anteriorly; 5 — habitus, dorsally; 6 — wing (5 — male; 4, 6 — female).

(4, 6 — redrawn from Hendel, 1909 b; 5 — original photo by D. Schulten)

Figs 7–10. *Chondrometopum bifenestratum*: 7, 8 — head anteriorly; 9, 10 — wing (7, 9 — male; 8, 10 — female).

(redrawn from Kameneva, 2004)

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